

Innovation of charcoal fused technology to increase the production of plants, safe and healthy

*Gusmailina¹⁾, Gustan Pari²⁾, Sri Komarayati³⁾
Forest Products Research and Development Center
Jl. Gunung Batu No. 5, Bogor 16610, Indonesia
Corresponding author: gsmlina@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Integrated charcoal is a technology that is done in an integrated manner in the process and the application. Charcoal is an innovation of environmentally friendly technology that can be applied to the community by utilizing various types of biomass waste as raw materials contained in the surrounding environment. Integrated charcoal technology (TAT) will produce charcoal, bioactive compost charcoal (arkoba) and liquid smoke, which can replace the existence of chemical fertilizers and pesticides. Integrated charcoal products (arkoba and liquid smoke) can support organic, safe and healthy cultivation system. Arkoba is given at the beginning of planting, while liquid smoke is given once a week. Several application trials of integrated charcoal products on various types of crops, both agricultural crops, plantations and forestry crops, provide better results than using chemical fertilizers and pesticides. The integrated charcoal product will certainly be very profitable for farmers, because it is easy and cheap to apply, as well as very beneficial to the environment, because it will reduce pollution due to excessive use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides. This paper presents a review of integrated charcoal technology and application in rice plants. important to be disseminated as beneficial to society and environment.

***Keywords:** integrated charcoal, arkoba, liquid smoke, plants, safe, healthy*

INTRODUCTION

Integrated charcoal is a technology with an integrated manner in the process and application. It is an environmentally friendly technological innovation that can be applied to the community by utilizing various types of biomass waste as raw materials contained in the surrounding environment (Gusmailina, *et al*, 2017a). From integrated charcoal technology (TAT), charcoal, bioactive compost charcoal and liquid smoke will be produced, which can replace the presence of chemical fertilizers and pesticides. The use of integrated

charcoal products (archeology and liquid smoke) can support organic, safe and healthy cultivation systems.

Integrated charcoal is an applied technology that is environmentally friendly, because it utilizes various types of biomass waste and applies low emission technology. Integrated charcoal technology produces charcoal, compost charcoal and liquid smoke. Charcoal is very much beneficial for life, not only used as fuel but can also be applied in agriculture and animal husbandry. The smoke formed in the process of making charcoal will change shape into a liquid when the cooling process occurs. This liquid is called liquid smoke or wood vinegar. Liquid smoke is also very beneficial for human life, both as a medicine for skin diseases (drugs for itching / acne), and for application in agriculture and animal husbandry.

Figure 1. Background of integrated charcoal production kiln, during the socialization of science and technology transfer in Gunung padang village, Cianjur district

Charcoal

Charcoal is not fertilizer materials, although charcoal contains several macro and micro elements but in very small amounts. Charcoal has pores on its surface, so that if charcoal is used as a mixture the planting medium can improve the circulation of water and air in the soil. In addition charcoal can increase soil pH so that this condition will provide space for the development of

soil microbes that function in the supply of nutrients in the soil which will later be absorbed by plants. Therefore charcoal is called as a builder of soil fertility. Some research results also show that the addition of charcoal to growing media can increase the growth of ecto and endo mycorrhizal spores in plants. So that it can accelerate plant growth both in the nursery and on the land (Gusmailina *et al.*, 2015). According Glaser, B (2002) and Lehmann *et al.* (2003), the effect of charcoal on soil fertility have scientifically proven.

Although not as fertilizer, charcoal can build the quality of soil conditions both physically, chemically and biologically. From some observations it turns out that the addition of charcoal can increase the microbial activity of the soil organic matter. It also can increase the population of N-binding bacteria in the soil. The application of charcoal to soil originating from waste is in accordance with the pattern of sustainable and environmentally sound development, because it can help solve the problem of waste while repairing acidic and critical lands, and making the soil stable. Charcoal characteristics are useful as an agent for builders, fertilizers while maintaining soil stability, so that charcoal has a role as a long-term life-giving agent in the soil and plants that grow on it (Gusmailina *et al.*, 2015).

Alkaline charcoal can increase the pH of acid so that it is very good to be used as a substitute for lime on acidic soils that are expanding in Indonesia. Charcoal has a high absorption of pesticide residues and chemical fertilizer residues that are in the soil, contain minerals that are useful for plant growth, and have large pores, thus providing good conditions for the development of soil microorganisms needed by plants. The application of charcoal on the ground is very necessary in the future, given the nature and role that is quite important. Therefore charcoal should not be seen as an energy and economic commodity, but has high ecological value, so that it is necessary to develop an integrated model of agriculture / livestock and forestry based on charcoal technology (Gusmailina *et al.*, 2015).

Bioactive compost charcoal (Arkoba)

Bioactive compost charcoal is a product of integrated charcoal technology, continued from the development of the functions and benefits of charcoal. A combination of charcoal and compost is produced through the composting process. Since 1999 the PKEHH research group (Processing of Chemicals and Forest Energy) the Center for Forest Products Research and Development has begun to develop products of compost-charcoal with the main raw material for charcoal is sawdust, while compost raw materials can be derived from organic agricultural waste, mangium litter, litter litter and litter a mixture of several types of trees. Adding charcoal to the composting process

aims to improving the quality of the compost. It is also hoped that the presence of charcoal in composting will increase the number and activity of microorganisms that play a role, so that the decomposition process can take place more quickly. From several trials of providing compost charcoal on the ground, in addition to increasing the availability of soil nutrients, improving soil physical, chemical and biological properties, It can also increase soil pH and soil CEC values, making it suitable for rehabilitation / reclamation of critical, increasingly widespread in Indonesia. Of the several applications of compost charcoal that have been tested, both in the laboratory and in the field, the growth of plants that were given compost charcoal increased by 2 times compared to those not given compost charcoal (Gusmailina *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 2. Bioaktif Charcoal compost

Liquid smoke

Liquid smoke or wood vinegar is an organic liquid / distillate obtained from the condensation of smoke in the carbonization process. The liquid is brownish yellow - black. Liquid smoke is produced from cooled smoke that can be made from various lignocellulose wastes with simple technology. The secret possessed by liquid smoke in addition to being acidic has a specific aroma and flavor, and also contains multi-purpose chemical components for humans, animals and plants such as acetic acid, phenol and methanol. This liquid smoke liquid can be used as a medicine for skin diseases, biopesticides, plant growth boosters, food preservatives, wood preservatives, room cleaners, anti-oxidants, anti-microbes, coagulants and odors in rubber processing, prevention of fungi and others (Komarayati and Gusmailina, 2014) Coconut shell liquid smoke contains phenol compounds, which can inhibit the growth of bacteria / fungi so that it can be used as a preservative or disinfectant (Slamet *et al.*, 20017). The raw materials used to make liquid smoke are widely available around us. According

to S. Wiyono *in* Rahimah (2014), liquid smoke contains alkaloids and secondary metabolites that can be used as pesticides. According to Hagner (2013), acetic and furfural acids contained in liquid smoke are compounds that have the ability to resist snail pests. Rejection of pests, due to the presence of these compounds simultaneously.

Figure 3. Liquid smoke P3HH

The Forest Products Research and Development Center has conducted research and development regarding the manufacture and application of liquid smoke since the 2000s. The application is mostly for the growth of various types of plants, both forestry plants and agricultural crops and plantations with significant results. Yatagai (2002) states that liquid smoke contains chemical components such as acetic acid which serves to accelerate plant growth and prevent plant diseases. Likewise, methanol and phenols and their derivatives act to prevent plant pests and diseases. The results of other studies say that liquid smoke is useful to improve soil quality and help plant growth to be better and stronger and more resistant to pests and diseases (Sinar Tani, 2010).

In agricultural fields, in addition liquid smoke contains macro nutrients also acts as growth hormone, as well as functioning as a natural pesticide for plants. In the field of charcoal and liquid smoke farms are also good as a mixture of feed, as well as to improve hygiene, cleanliness and health of livestock pens. Charcoal is used as a cage lining to reduce odors, also makes the cage always warm and absorb various diseases that will attack livestock, so that livestock become healthy and the environment becomes clean. Likewise liquid smoke can be sprayed around the cattle shed to repel odors and insects / flies in livestock manure.

Integrated Charcoal Technology Application (TAT)

Since 2015, the Forest Products Research and Development Center, Bogor has socialized this TAT to various community groups and government

agencies in several pilot locations. The demonstration plot was built as a model for the community to prove that TAT can be applied easily and cheaply. The activity begins with a demonstration of ways to produce TAT products, then applied to plants planted in demonstration plots. The demonstration plot was made to prove to the community that TAT products can be used to support the success of crop cultivation, without using chemical products such as chemical fertilizers and pesticides. So that the results obtained are classified as organic products that have a higher value and selling price than the products produced from non-organic cultivation.

The TAT product demonstration plot in Ciranjang, Cianjur Regency on rice plants showed that rice grown using archeology (at the beginning of planting only) with 9-10 times spraying liquid smoke during the planting season, without using chemical fertilizers and pesticides at all, gave more rice production better than rice grown using chemical fertilizers and pesticides. Application of archeology and liquid smoke in an integrated manner in lowland rice plants is not attacked by pests and rats, rice grains are more dense and filled and not broken, do not easily collapse, formerly harvested rice fields that use Arkoba and liquid smoke leave softer black soil marks and not easily hard and cracked, even though it has been exposed to sunlight for 2 days. Financially more profitable than non-organically grown rice (Gusmailina *et al.*, 2017 b).

Figure 4. Application of integrated charcoal products in rice demonstration plots in Ciranjang

TAT product demonstration plots (archeology and liquid smoke) on forest plants was planted in agroforestry land for 6 months on 4 tree species in Babakan Karet Village, Cianjur Regency, which increase the growth of mahogany trees 5 times, rambutan 7 times, sengon 6 times; and durian trees 3 times compared to those not given TAT products.

**DEMPLOT Application of integrated charcoal products
(ARKOBA + ASAP CAIR) at Agroforestry Land
Ds. Babakan Karet, Cianjur
Durian, Rambutan, Sengon, Mahony, Coffee plants**

**Increase growth 3-4 times
for 6 months of observation**

Figure 5. Application integrated charcoal products on some plants

Demonstration plot application of TAT products (arkoba and liquid smoke) in coffee plants grown in the demonstration plot of Gunung Padang village, Cianjur regency, for 5 months of observation showed that, plant growth increased 3-4 times compared to those not given archeology and liquid smoke. Coffee plant growth figures are stronger and have leaves that are fresh and shiny. Therefore, this integrated charcoal technology and application be disseminated, so that it is beneficial for the community and the environment.

Figure 6. Application integrated charcoal products on coffee plant

Figure 7. Integrated charcoal technology scheme

CONCLUSION

Integrated Charcoal Technology (TAT) is a solution of various national problems that exist today, among others: the problem of waste / waste that results in environmental pollution, environmental health, improvement and improvement in the quality of land fertility while improving food quality through the application of organic cultivation supported by integrated charcoal products, empowerment the community through increasing understanding and awareness of good and useful environmental management, as well as growing employment and increasing family income which leads to increased family welfare.

Integrated charcoal is an applied technology that is environmentally friendly, because it utilizes various types of biomass waste and applies low emission technology. Integrated charcoal technology produces charcoal, compost charcoal and liquid smoke which has many benefits for life, both as alternative fuels, as well as to increase the productivity of agricultural and plantation land and crops. Smoke formed in the process of making charcoal, will change shape to liquid when the cooling process occurs. This liquid is called liquid smoke or wood vinegar, it is also very much beneficial for human life, both as a medicine for skin diseases (hives / zits), as well as to be applied in agriculture and animal husbandry, because in addition to containing macro nutrients also acts as a growth hormone, and also functions as a natural

pesticide for plants. This activity is essentially an effort to empower the community, business world and other parties in the development of forestry and the environment in general. It is also an investment to secure and preserve natural resources as state assets. So that this activity has a strategic role, both in order to increase the capacity and independence of the community, as well as in efforts to preserve natural resources, while helping to overcome various waste problems.

REFERENCES

- Glaser, B, J Lehmann and W. Zech. 2002. Ameliorating physical and chemical properties of highly weathered soils in the tropics with charcoal – A review. *Biol & Fertility of Soils* 35, 219–230.
- Gusmailina, Sri Komarayati, dan G. Pari. 2015. Membangun Kesuburan Lahan dengan Arang. Pusat Penelitian dan Pengembangan Hasil Hutan. Badan Litbang dan Inovasi Kementerian LHK. Bogor.
- Gusmailina, G. Pari dan S. Komarayati. 2016. Pengelolaan Sampah Dengan Model “Three In One” Untuk Nano-Biofertilizer Dalam Rangka Mitigasi Dan Adaptasi Lingkungan. Laporan Kegiatan Pengembangan. Tahun 2016. Pusat Penelitian dan Pengembangan Hasil Hutan. Bogor.
- Gusmailina, Sri Komarayati, G. Pari, dan D. Hendra. 2017a. Teknologi Arang Terpadu. Makalah pada Acara Alih Iptek Arang Terpadu, Kerjasama Forum Komunikasi Peneliti dengan Widyaiswara, Penyuluh dan Guru SKMA di Pusat Diklat Kehutanan. Bogor, April 2017.
- Gusmailina, Sri Komarayati, G. Pari, dan N. Jaajah. 2017b. Demontrasi plot (Demplot) percontohan arkoba + asap cair dari sampah organik pada lahan padi di Desa Kertajaya, Ciranjang, Kabupaten Cianjur. Forpro. Majalah Ilmiah Populer Bidang Keteknikan Kehutanan dan Pengolahan Hasil Hutan. Vol. 6 No.1. Edisi Juni 2017. Pusat Litbang Hasil Hutan, Bogor.
- Hagner, 2013. Potential of the slow pyrolysis products birchar oil wood vinegar and biochar in sustainable plant protection-pesticidal effects, soil improvement and environmental risks. Dissertation. University of Helsinki 42p. Finland.
- Komarayati, S., dan Gusmailina. 2014. Rahasia dibalik asap cair. *Makalah poster pada Seminar Hasil Penelitian PUSTEKOLAH* di Bogor, Nopember 2014.
- Lehmann, J, J.P. da Silva Jr, C. Steiner, T. Nehls, W. Zech, and B. Glaser. 2003. Nutrient availability and leaching in an archaeological anthrosol

and a ferralsol of the Central Amazon basin: fertilizer, manure and charcoal amendments. *Plant and Soil* 249: 343–357.

Rahimah, D.S. 2014. Asap usir elmaut. *Trubus*, no. 536, Juli 2014/XLV.

Sinar Tani. 2010. Cuka kayu penyubur dan penguat tanaman. *Sinar Tani edisi? Membangun Kemandirian Agribisnis*. Diakses tanggal 21 Nopember, 2010. Jakarta.